

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERSONALITY DISPOSITIONS OF DRUG
ABUSERS & NON- DRUG ABUSERS**

Education

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Introduction:

The word Personality, itself holds fascination for the general public. Most of the popular meanings fall under one of two headings. The first use is related to social skill or adroitness. The personality of an individual may be assessed by the effectiveness with which he or she is able to elicit positive reactions from various persons under different conditions. Therefore when a teacher refers to a student as presenting a personality problem is probably indicating the inadequacy of his social skills to maintain satisfactory relations with his fellow students and the teacher. The second use considers the personality of an individual to consist of the most outstanding or salient impression that he or she creates in others. A person may therefore be said to have a "submissive personality" or a "fearful personality". Allport (1937) in an exhaustive survey of the literature extracted almost fifty different definitions. Allportdistinguishties between biosocial and biophysical definitions. The biosocial definitions shows that it is the reaction of other individuals to the subject that define the subject's personality. The biophysical definition relates personality firmly in characteristics or qualities of the subject. Personality thus has an organic as well as a perceived side and may be linked to specific qualities of the individual that are susceptible to objective description and measurement.

Another important definition is the omnibus definition. This definition embraces personality by enumeration. The term personality is used here to include everything about the individual. Other definitions place primary emphasis upon the integrative or organisational function of personality. Personality is that which gives order and congruence to all the different kinds of behaviour in which the individual engages. A number of theorists have chosen to emphasise the function of personality in mediating the adjustment of the individual. Personality consists of the varied and yet typical efforts at adjustment that are carried out by the individual. Some psychologists have considered personality to represent the essence of the human condition. Allport's suggestion that 'personality is what a man really is' illustrates that personality consists of what, is most typical and deeply characteristic of the person.

Personality dispositions are of special interest to all educationists. It is a phrase that includes everything from high anxiety to low self-esteem, immaturity to depression. There are

various reports that show that moderate to heavy use of drugs leads to a number of personality problems among college students. Drug use is part of a behaviour pattern that interacts and influences personality, attitudes and values. Most drug users seek an altered state of consciousness, a different perception of the world than is provided by daily life activities. The individual's customary reaction to external threats of pain and destruction with which it is not prepared to cope is to become afraid. Overwhelmed by excessive stimulation that the ego is unable to bring under control, the becomes flooded with anxiety. Anxiety is thus a state of tension. Anxiety reduces a person to a state of infantile helplessness. When the ego cannot cope with anxiety by rational methods it has to fall back upon unrealistic ones like drug intake. Personality develops in response to four major sources of tension (i) Physiological growth processes (ii) frustrations (iii) conflicts and (iv) threats. As a direct consequence of increases in tension emanating from these sources, the person is forced to learn new methods of reducing tension (Freud, 1959). Hence Drugs seen to be initiated as one of the ways to reduce tension but later lead to changes in Personality dispositions of the drug addicts. The Personality traits linked with early or frequent drug use include, rebelliousness, non-conformity, resistance to authority, high tolerance of deviance and strong need for independence or normlessness.

Cattell's Theory of Personality:

The personality theory of Cattell is the most comprehensive and is based on factor analysis. Cattell was impressed by the pioneer work of Spearman and the extensive developments by Thurstone. His theoretical formulations are closely related to McDougall's. Cattell, provides a very general definition of personality. 'Personality is that which permits a prediction of what a person will do in a given situation. The goal of psychological research in personality is thus to establish laws about what different people will do in all kinds of social and general environmental situation. Personality is concerned with all the behaviour of the individual, both overt and under the skin'. Cattell views personality as a complex and differentiated structure of traits, with its motivation largely dependent upon a subset of these, the so-called dynamic traits.

Methodology:

The study is a normative type of survey. The population of this study covers all the postgraduate students of the affiliated colleges of MJPRohilkhandUniversity. In this study students from different departments of the affiliated colleges i.e. Arts, Science, Education, Law and Commerce have been selected. The selection of sample was completed on the basis of systematic sampling. In all total number of college selected came to be six. At the second stage of sampling it was decided to select only two faculties from each college since taking all the students from each college would make the sample very large.

Sample:

The size of the sample thus obtained was 468. This sample was afterwards broken into two sub groups on the basis of the scores obtained by these students on the Drug Abuse Questionnaire. These two groups were named as the group of Drug Abusers and the group of Non-Drug Abusers. The size of these groups worked out to be 79 and 389 respectively. The

groups were administered the following tools:

TOOL USED:

Cattle's 16 PF Test by Raymond B. Cattle

The 16 PF test was used to find out the personality dispositions of Drug Abusers and Non-Drug Abusers on all the sixteen factors presented in the test.

DRUG ABUSE QUESTIONNAIRE

Drug Abuse Questionnaire was developed on the basis of available related literature as well as on the basis of discussions with experienced research specialists, interviews with principals, researchers and senior teachers of reputed colleges and universities.

The following eight areas in which the study of drug abusers may be distributed were considered to be the man purview of the study:

1. Family conditions
2. Level of income
3. Educational factors
4. Drug habit
5. Health problems
6. Role Model
7. Effects of Drugs on Behaviour
8. Future Plans.

The formal questionnaire consisting of 70 items was prepared in which each item was related to one of the eight areas mentioned above. Modifications were made after tryout and pre-test and then the questionnaire consisting of 32 items was given a final shape.

ADMINISTRATION OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE:

Final 'Drug Abuse Questionnaire' was administered top 600 selected postgraduate students of colleges affiliated to RohilkhandUniversity. All the questionnaires were filled in the college departments, as the investigator approached them personality by visiting the colleges and requested the students to fill the questionnaire. They were given a total time of one hour to return the booklet.

Results of the 16 PF test

Distribution (Group)	Personality Factor	MEAN	S.D.	't' value
1	2	3	4	5
I	'B'	17.544	5.002	.52 non-significant at .05 and 01 level
II		17.848	2.729	
I	'C'	36.949	5.512	2.182 significant at .05 but non-significant at .01
II		39.131	6.108	

I	'E'	24.608	4.292	2.00 significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		22.971	4.981	
I	'F'	40.696	5.280	2.972 significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		38.702	6.149	
I	'G'	33.658	4.905	5.04 significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		30.766	4.596	
I	'H'	39.645	5.925	8.22 significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		29.663	10.457	
I	'I'	21.228	4.602	0.76 non-significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		20.470	8.679	
I	'L'	16.911	5.255	1.33 non-significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		15.972	7.721	
I	'M'	23.810	5.426	2.16 significant at .05 but non-significant at .01 level
II		22.159	9.061	
I	'N'	22.544	5.579	1.33 and significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		21.619	5.914	
I	'O'	21.392	6.753	1.73 non-significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		19.738	11.544	
I	'Q ₁ '	19.139	4.626	4.12 significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		16.545	6.993	
I	'Q ₂ '	22.899	6.650	1.66 non-significant at .05 and .01 levels
II		21.550	6.557	
I	'Q ₃ '	29.152	6.874	2.04 significant at .05 level but non-significant at .01 levels
II		27.478	5.310	
I	'Q ₄ '	23.532	9.189	0.3 non-significant at both .05 and .01 levels
II		23.499	11.382	

I = Drug Abuser (N = 79);

II = Non-Drug Abuser (N = 389)

Out of the sixteenth factors for which results have been obtained in the 16 PF test, only

eight factors show a significant difference between drug abusers and non-drug abusers. These factors are C, E, F, G, H, M, Q₁ and Q₃, the remaining eight factors do not show any significant difference between the personality dispositions of drug abusers and non-drug abusers.

Personality 'Factor C'

Distribution	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' value
Group I Drug Abusers	79	36.949	5.512	2.182
Group II Non-Drug Abusers	389	39.131	6.108	

It is seen from the Table above, that the mean value for non-drug abusers 39.13 is much higher than the mean value of drug abusers i.e. 36.95 on factor C, which denotes that higher value on this factor means that a person is more stable, faces reality, calm and mature. The mean difference for both the groups is significant at .05 level.. The results of this study show that non-drug abusers possess greater ego-strength, better morale and are matured than drug abusers.

Here the factor E is characterized by traits like humble, mild, accommodating and conforming, in the low-score direction. The mean value clearly shows that drug abusers have a higher mean value i.e. 34.60 than their counterpart, non-drug abusers who have a mean value of 22.97. The 't' value is significant at both .05 and .01 levels. It is therefore clear that non-drug abusers are more humble, mild, accommodating and conforming as compared to drug abusers who may be a little more aggressive and assertive.

As seen in the figure above, the mean value of drug abusers is 40.696 which is quite high as compared to the mean value of non abusers which is 38.702. The 't' value of 2.972 therefore is significant at .05 and .01 level. Therefore, the drug abusers (with a higher mean value) are impulsive and mercurial. They are more carefree, happy go lucky and impulsively lively as compared to non-drug abusers.

The mean value of drug abusers, (i.e. 33.658) is higher than the mean score of non-drug abusers (i.e. 30.766), This value is significant at .05 level. The characteristics listed in the manual for Factor 'G' are persevering, staid, stronger ego-strength, preferring hard-working people to witty companions, if the score is high. Since the mean score of drug abusers is higher, they are somewhat more staid, and contentious and prefer hard working people to witty companions. Since the study deals with students enrolled for post-graduation who need to attend classes regularly, therefore it seems likely that majority of them are hard-working individuals who tend to remain rule-bound.

The Figure above, shows that the mean value of non-drug abusers is 29.663 which is lower than the mean value of drug abusers which is 39.645. The manual states that the person who scores high on factor H is sociable, bold ready to try new things, spontaneous and abundant in emotional response. His 'thick-skinnedness' enable him to face wear and tear in dealing with people and gruelling emotional situations without fatigue. It is therefore clear from the results obtained that drug abusers are more spontaneous, venturesome, socially bold. He can be careless for detail, ignore danger signals and tend to be "pushy" and actively interested in the opposite sex. The non-drug abusers with a low score possess traits like shy, restrained and timid.

. As shown above, the mean value on factor 'M' for drug abusers and non-drug abusers are 23.810 and 22.159 respectively. Here high scores on factor 'M' are characterised by personality traits like imaginative, wrapped up in inner urgencies, careless of practical matters,

absent minded. The mean value of drug abusers (23.810) is higher than that of the non-drug abusers (22.159). The 't' value, is significant at .05 level but does not reach 2.58 and therefore is non significant at .01 level. It is clear from the mean values that the drug abusers are more unconventional, unconcerned over everyday matters, imaginative as compared to their counterpart, the non-drug abusers. Further, implications of this factor are that a person who attains a higher score (here drug abusers) tend to have inner directed interests which sometimes lead to unrealistic situations accompanied by progressive outbursts.

. As seen in the figure above, the mean values of drug abusers (i.e. 19.139) is higher than the mean value of non-drug abusers (i.e. 16.545). The 't' value of 4.12, therefore is significant at both .05 and .01 level.. The higher mean score of drug abusers for factor Q₁ is characterised by, experimenting, critical, liberal, analytical and free-thinking. According to the manual, the person who scores high on factor Q₁ (here drug abusers) tends to be interested in intellectual matters but has doubts on fundamental issues. He is skeptical and inquiring regarding ideas, either old or new. He tends to be informed, less inclined to moralize, more inclined to experiment in life generally. In contrast to these traits, a person scoring low on factor Q₁ (here-drug abusers) is conservative i.e. accepts the "tried and true", is confident in what has been taught to believe, is cautious and compromising in regard to new ideas and a inclined to go along with tradition.

The 't' values thus obtained can be seen in the figure above. The 't' value of 2.04 is significant at 0.5 level but is non-significant at .01 level. It is seen in the table above that mean value of abusers i.e. 29.152 is higher than the mean value of non-abusers (i.e. 27.478). Conclusion can be thus drawn that drug abusers have a behaviour which is inclined to be socially aware and evidences what is termed self respect. They sometimes tend to be obstinate. According to the manual effective leaders and some paranoids are high on Q₃. In contrast, the non-drug abusers do not have a very strong control of their emotions and are careful in their general behaviour.

RESULTS:

Results of the 16 PF Test indicate that out of the sixteen factors only seven factors show a significant difference between drug abusers and non-drug abusers. These factors are C,E,F, G, H, M, Q₁, Q₃. The remaining eight factors do not show any significant difference between drug abusers and non-drug abusers. The results indicate that non-drug abusers are emotionally more mature stable and realistic about the (implications of factor C in the manual) as compared to the drug abusers. Results of factor C also indicate that this group of non-drug abusers possesses greater ego-strength better group morale than the drug abusers. A higher mean value (24.60%) of drug abusers for Factor 'E' indicates that they are somewhat aggressive less humble and more stubborn at times. Results of Factor 'F' show that drug abusers are more impulsively lively happy go lucky and carefree individuals. According to the characteristics listed in the manual for factor G it is clear that drug abusers are staid and consencious. Values obtained for Factor H indicate that non-drug abusers are more venturesome uninhibited, spontaneous and abundant in emotional response. They are also able to face gruelling emotional situations without fatigue. Results for factor 'M' show that drug abusers are more imaginative though wrapped up in inner urgencies and careless of practical matters. Further implications of this factor are that this group of drug abuses has inner directed interests which sometimes lead to unrealistic situations accompanied by expressive out-bursts. Conclusion from results of Factor Q₁ can be drawn that drug abusers are more experimenting, analytical free, thinking and critical. The results obtained in Factor Q₃ indicate that drug abusers have a behaviour which is inclined to be socially aware

and evidences what is termed self respect. They sometimes tend to be obstinate.

CONCLUSIONS:

The drug abusers appear to be somewhat aggressive less humble and more stubborn at times, in their personality disposition. They are also carefree, happy go lucky individuals. They are more imaginative through wrapped up in inner urgencies and may be careless of practical matters. This group of drug abusers has inner-directed interests which sometimes lead to unrealistic situations accompanied by expressive outbursts.

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